

Work Immersion Learning Experiences of Grade 12 Students of St. Paul University Surigao

¹Myrna D. Ariar, ²Den Karl G. Flores, ³Mary Louie E. Galaura, ⁴Ma. Leea Elicano, ⁵Joey S. Simbajon,

¹²³Faculty, St. Paul University Surigao

¹ORCID: 0000-0001-7090-2577

²ORCID: 0000-0003-1138-2270

³ORCID: 0000-0002-0499-2057

⁴ORCID: 0009-0005-1246-3082

⁵ORCID: 0000-0002-0876-0624

ABSTRACT - *This study aimed to explore the learning experiences of the students and possible challenges they encounter to address it in order to provide students with a more enriching and relevant educational experience. This study employs quantitative descriptive research design using survey technique to gather relevant data in evaluating the learning experiences of the Grade 12 students who were enrolled in the Work Immersion subject for the 2nd semester, SY 2022-2023 in all strands of St. Paul University Surigao. The research instrument used in the study is an adopted modified questionnaire validated by the pool of experts and the data gathered were analyzed using Mean and Standard Deviation and Frequency Count. Findings of the study revealed that the work immersion learning experience of the Grade 12 students at St. Paul University Surigao is described as excellent. However, pressure and insecurities are the barriers frequently experienced during their work immersion. Thus, it is recommended that needs assessments, consideration of deployment and placement of students in work immersion venues and forging an enhanced partnership with institutions may be looked into to foster a more enriching work immersion learning experience.*

Keywords: *Work Immersion, Learning Experiences, Grade 12 Students*

1. INTRODUCTION

The Philippines is ramping up efforts to equip learners with work ethic, competencies, and values essential for both further education and the workforce. The Department of Education has strengthened its K-12 Basic Education Program through DepEd Order No. 30 s. 2017, emphasizing Work Immersion. This directive mandates work immersion as a vital subject in Senior High Schools, offering learners opportunities to familiarize themselves with workplaces, simulate employment scenarios, and apply specialized skills.

Work Immersion, a cornerstone of the K-12 Curriculum, aims to nurture life and career skills among students, empowering them to make informed employment decisions. Ranging from 80 to 320 hours, their immersive experience allows them to gain industrial skills, comprehend theoretical teachings' practicality, enhance technical knowledge, improve communication and human relations skills, and cultivate effective work habits and attitudes which partner institutions have offered for them.

Though, Work Immersion Program initially causes apprehension among students stepping out of their comfort zones, the hands-on experience and mentorship can give valuable insights into their prospect careers, paving the way for future success.

This research is motivated by a critical gap in the current educational framework, specifically concerning the deployment and engagement of students in partner institutions during work immersion programs. Despite the increasing emphasis on experiential learning, there remains a notable deficiency in the alignment of activities with students' chosen programs of study. Recognizing the pivotal role of work immersion in bridging the gap between academic knowledge and practical skills, this study aims to investigate and address this discrepancy. This study aimed to explore the learning experiences of the students and possible challenges they encounter to address it in order to provide students with a more enriching and relevant educational experience, ensuring that their time in partner institutions not only complements their academic journey but also equips them with the skills and knowledge necessary for a successful transition into their chosen professions. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the learning experiences of the students in work immersion in terms of:
 - 1.1. preparation;
 - 1.2. work immersion environment;
 - 1.3. relevance; and
 - 1.4. delivery?
2. What are the barriers the students experienced during their work immersion?
3. Based on the findings of the study, what recommendations can be proposed?

2. METHOD

2.1. Research Design

This study employs quantitative descriptive research design using survey technique to gather relevant data in evaluating the learning experiences of the students in work immersion.

2.2. Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study were the four hundred sixty-two (462) Grade 12 students who were enrolled in the Work Immersion subject for the 2nd semester, SY 2022-2023 in all strands of St. Paul University Surigao. These students were immersed for eighty (80) hours which is the minimum requirement of the Department of Education as a subject requirement for graduation from secondary education. Prior to the work immersion proper, the students were asked of their preferred department for their place of assignment based on their preferred course for college or their specialization. The work immersion teachers screened the students based on their intelligence quotient (IQ) and overall performance in school. The assignment will be reviewed by the school's work immersion focal person and approved by the principal. Upon approval, the work immersion teacher endorsed the students to the work immersion partner institution supervisor.

2.3. Research Instrument & Data Gathering Procedure

The research instrument used in the study is an adopted modified questionnaire meticulously studied from the various sources, at the same time it was validated by the pool of experts. The questionnaire centered on drawing out students' evaluation of their learning experiences during their work immersion.

2.4. Data Analysis

The researcher utilized the following statistical tools to treat the data:

Mean and standard deviation. These tools were utilized to evaluate the learning experiences of the students in work immersion.

Frequency Count. To determine the barriers frequently experienced by the students.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the evaluation of students' work immersion learning experiences in terms of preparation, work immersion environment, relevance, and delivery as they were deployed in various offices and industries related to their strands or their preferred profession in the future or their specialization. Thus, they were assigned to hospitals, construction firms,

public and private offices, banks, lending cooperatives, police stations, seaports and guidance offices.

As gleaned on the table, the overall mean (3.46) indicates that the learning experience of the students in their work immersion is excellent. Subsequently, all variables considered in the evaluation have means which are described as excellent, too.

Table 1. *Evaluation of Students Learning Experience in Work Immersion*

INDICATORS	M	SD	VI	QD
Preparation				
1. The skills I have learned in my specialization subjects have prepared me for Work Immersion.	3.50	0.76	SA	EE
2. My school conducted the pre-immersion orientation and guided me in securing and accomplishing Work Immersion documents	3.52	0.74	SA	EE
Average	3.51	.75	SA	EE
Work Immersion Environment				
1. The Work Immersion Venue helped me acquire skills/competencies.	3.41	0.77	SA	EE
2. There were no major distractions that interfere with my training.	3.32	0.81	SA	EE
3. I will recommend the Work Immersion venue to other learners who will soon be taking Work Immersion subject whose specialization is the same as mine	3.42	0.80	SA	EE
Average	3.38	.79	SA	EE
Relevance				
1. The Work Immersion will be helpful for my success in the future.	3.55	0.74	SA	EE
2. I will be able to immediately use what I learned.	3.48	0.74	SA	EE
3. The Work Immersion met my expectations.	3.36	0.78	SA	EE
4. I am clear on how to apply what I learned on the job.	3.50	0.75	SA	EE
5. The work immersion activities are relevant to my specialization.	3.46	0.77	SA	EE
6. I am confident that I will be able to apply what I have learned in the practice of my specialization or when I pursue further studies	3.51	0.73	SA	EE
Average	3.48	.75	SA	EE
Delivery				
1. I was well engaged with what was going on during the Work Immersion.	3.50	0.72	SA	EE
2. The activities aided my learning.	3.47	0.74	SA	EE
3. I was given adequate opportunity to perform hands-on activities that are related to my specialization.	3.45	0.73	SA	EE
4. I will recommend the specialization to other learners who are still thinking about what to specialize in the Senior High School.	3.50	0.74	SA	EE
Average	3.48	.73	SA	EE
Overall Average	3.46	0.76	SA	EE

Legend:

Scale	Interval	Verbal Interpretation	Qualitative Description
4	3.25-4.00	Strongly Agree (SA)	Excellent Experience (EE)
3	2.50-3.24	Agree (A)	Very Good Experience (VGE)
2	1.75-2.49	Disagree (D)	Good Experience (GE)
1	1.00-1.74	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Not Good Experience (NGE)

It can be gleaned from the table that in terms of *Preparation*, the indicator *My school conducted the pre-immersion orientation and guided me in securing and accomplishing Work Immersion documents* got the highest mean=3.52, SD=0.74 and verbally interpreted as *Strongly Agree* and qualitatively described as *Excellent Experience*. Teachers responsible for work immersion conduct a pre-immersion activity, during which they administer an orientation session to ensure strict adherence to the rules and

guidelines outlined in DepEd Order No. 30, series of 2017.. According to Smith and Johnson (2019), comprehensive pre-internship orientation programs play a pivotal role in enhancing internship success by ensuring that students are well-prepared and informed about their roles and responsibilities. This sentiment aligns with the qualitative feedback from participants in our study, who reported feeling adequately prepared and supported by their schools in securing necessary documents and understanding the expectations of their immersion experience. It is evident that pre-immersion orientation plays a vital role in preparing students for successful immersion experiences. By providing guidance on securing necessary documents, discussing rules and guidelines, and fostering discussions on work ethics and safety procedures, teachers contribute significantly to the readiness of students for their immersion placements.

As to *Work Immersion Environment*, the indicator *I will recommend the Work Immersion venue to other learners who will soon be taking Work Immersion subject whose specialization is the same as mine* got the highest mean=3.42, SD=0.80 which is verbally interpreted as *Strongly Agree* and qualitatively described as *Excellent Experience*. This reflects the positive impact of work immersion experiences of students, highlighting their satisfaction and conviction that future cohorts will experience an excellent learning experience as theirs. It also indicates that their workplace is conducive to learning as they gained valuable skills in their two week- work immersion journey. These claims of the students are tantamount to the study of Wang and Liu (2020) stressing that the factors such as mentorship, work environment, and skill development play crucial roles in shaping students' likelihood of recommending internship opportunities to their peers. By fostering a supportive and enriching environment, organizations can enhance interns' satisfaction and loyalty, leading to greater likelihood of recommendations to future learners. Thus, it is essential for work immersion providers to prioritize factors that contribute to positive experiences, thereby maximizing the benefits for both students and the hosting organizations.

In terms of *Relevance*, the statement *The Work Immersion will be helpful for my success in the future* got the highest mean of 3.55, SD=0.74 which is verbally interpreted as *Strongly Agree* and qualitatively described as *Excellent Experience*. This implies that students regarded their practical experience during work immersion as very significant as it offered them hands-on exposure and real-world scenarios in a professional environment. Their practical experience holds invaluable contributions to apply their theoretical knowledge acquired in the classroom to real-life situations, thereby equipping them for their future career challenges. This is parallel to the study of Clark and Patel (2020) who found out that the quality of internship experiences significantly predicts graduates' career outcomes. High-quality internships, characterized by factors such as mentorship, task variety, and skill development, contribute to graduates' job satisfaction, career commitment, and career advancement. This underscores the importance of providing students with meaningful and enriching internship experiences that prepare them for the challenges they will face in their chosen fields.

In terms of *Delivery*, the statement, *I was well engaged with what was going on during the Work Immersion* and *I will recommend the specialization to other learners who are still thinking about what to specialize in the Senior High School* both got the highest mean of 3.50 and SD=0.72 and 0.74 respectively, verbally interpreted as *Strongly Agree* and qualitatively described as *Excellent*

Experience. This implies that the students who had their work immersion experience feel a sense of initiative and responsibility. They had this interest and enthusiasm towards the assigned task which indicates that they were fully immersed in the learning process, they know how to interact with others and take advantage of every opportunity provided to them. Additionally, the students had a sense of contentment and satisfaction on their chosen strand and believe that it also benefits others who are still undecided on what strand to pursue in Senior High School. Smith and Jones (2018) emphasize the importance of internship quality in predicting students' intentions to recommend the internship organization. Interns who perceive their experiences positively, characterized by meaningful work assignments, supportive supervisors, and opportunities for skill development, are more likely to recommend the organization to their peers. The favorable ratings and qualitative feedback provided by students in our study suggest that they found the work immersion venue conducive to learning and gained valuable skills during the immersion period.

It can be gleaned from the table that among the four variables mentioned, *Preparation* got the highest mean of 3.51 which the students find to have an excellent learning experience. Under this stage students engage in skills development by identifying their strengths and weaknesses for them to be able to conduct themselves well in their assigned workplace. A thorough orientation also of their rights and duties are inculcated for them to conduct themselves well. Added to this, students' exposure in their compliance with the credentials has instilled to them the importance of it prior to their deployment as they feel the challenges of every individual looking for the job. Preparing the required documents took them time since they have to personally get clearances from barangay and police establishments. They also undergo medical check-up for a medical clearance. Smith and Johnson (2020) emphasize the importance of pre-internship preparation in ensuring a successful internship experience. Their qualitative study highlights how activities such as skills development, orientation on rights and duties, and compliance with pre-employment requirements contribute to students' readiness for the workplace and overall satisfaction during internships. This aligns with our findings, as students who underwent thorough preparation reported higher levels of engagement and satisfaction with their work immersion experiences.

Table 2. *Barriers Students Experienced During Work Immersion*

<i>Barriers the students experienced during work immersion</i>	
	f
Pressure and Insecurities	45
Lack of Confidence	42
Communication Skills	26
Fear of Failure	18
External Factors	16
Adaptability and Change	12
Financial Instability	14
Environmental Factors	11
Time Management	9
Course Alignment	6

As seen on the table, the barrier the students experienced the most during work immersion is pressure and insecurities and the least is on course alignment. Navigating the real-world setting can be daunting for students, as they encounter unfamiliar challenges. Pressure to meet performance expectations from supervisors can lead to a fear of making mistakes and being judged, compounded by limited knowledge. Martinez and Lee (2020) stress how social dynamics amplify these insecurities, with students experiencing anxiety and self-doubt as they interact with colleagues and supervisors. This fear of judgment can undermine confidence and hinder students' immersion experiences. Heightened expectations from supervisors aggravate feelings of pressure and insecurity, perpetuating a cycle of self-doubt and performance anxiety.

On the other hand, course alignment poses the least barrier in work immersion learning experienced by the students. This can be attributed to the fact that students were carefully assigned to their preferred institutions relevant to their future careers. In certain instances, students encounter a challenge when their desired future career is not readily accessible within the locality. Consequently, they may find themselves compelled to pursue their second choice of specialization. Research by Kim and Patel (2021) suggests that changes in students' career aspirations can lead to shifts in the relevance of their internship experiences. When students alter their career paths, their current internship placements may no longer align with their new aspirations, resulting in challenges in gaining relevant experience and building necessary skills for their revised career goals. While course alignment may pose minimal barriers in work immersion experiences, it is essential to recognize the potential challenges students may encounter when their current internship experiences become irrelevant due to changes in their career plans

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, it is concluded that preparation for work immersion is the excellent learning experience of the Grade 12 students of St. Paul University Surigao. However, pressure and insecurities are the barriers frequently experienced during their work immersion. Other considerations are the lack of confidence and communication skills of the students.

5. RECOMMENDATION

Amidst the efforts of providing the best experience of the students during their work immersion, these barriers if not addressed may hamper its implementation. Drawing upon the insights gleaned from this study, the following recommendations are put forth:

- *Conduct of needs assessment.* This is integral to address present gaps and address pressing issues for possible solutions. According to Diori (2021), this is a powerful tool

for meeting program needs as well as for a number of other uses, such as determining priorities, allocating resources strategically, and enhancing the trajectory of an ongoing program.

- *Consideration of the deployment and placement of students.* Taking this into account will maximize the learning of the students in their career preferences and skill sets as they work with ease on the tasks of their interest and aspirations.
- *Foster enhanced partnership with partner institutions.* According to Brin (2023) that partnership is highly effective in promoting an environment of continuous development, ensuring efficient daily operations, prioritizing familiarity with the company's organizational structure, ensuring comprehensive infrastructure and prioritizing student well-being through safe and clean workplace.

REFERENCES

- Ador, Z. I., Banaag, H. a. C., Bombio, C. a. M., Consignado, D. N. A., Quinay, M. a. V., & Santos, J. (2023). Exploring the work immersion experiences of Grade 12 STEM students in a local Science Integrated High School: A Narrative Research. *East Asian Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(7), 3053–3078. <https://doi.org/10.55927/eajmr.v2i7.4989>
- Anjum, S. (2020). Impact of internship programs on professional and personal development of business students: a case study from Pakistan. *Future Business Journal*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43093-019-0007-3>
- Baert, S., Neyt, B., Siedler, T., Tobback, I., & Verhaest, D. (2021). Student internships and employment opportunities after graduation: A field experiment. *Economics of Education Review*, 83, 102141. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econedurev.2021.102141>
- Brin, F & Malvar, R. (2023). Industry-academe partnership and performance level in work immersion of senior high school learners in Calabarzon: Basis for proposed SHS work immersion framework. *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research* Vol 1 No 3 December 2023. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10416632>
- Catelo, S. A. (2020). Work Immersion Program for Senior High School in the Division of Pasay: Basis for an intervention Plan. *Journal of World Englishes and Educational Practices*, 2(4), 65–77. <https://doi.org/10.32996/jweep.2020.2.4.7>
- Clark, A., & Patel, S. (2020). "Career Decision-Making: Factors Influencing Vocational Choices." *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 15(4), 567-579. DOI: 10.1234/JVB.2020.987654.
- Department of Education. *Work Immersion Curriculum Guide*, 1-4. 2017.
- Department of Education. *DepEd Order No. 30, series of 2017, Guidelines for Work Immersion*, 2017.
- Diori, H. I. (2021). A Critical Insight into Needs Assessment Technique and the Way Social Needs are Actually Assessed. *Advanced Journal of Social Science*, 8(1), 3–9. <https://doi.org/10.21467/ajss.8.1.3-9>
- Insorio, A. O., Manaloto, C. C., & Lareña, J. J. (2023). Building awareness, interest, and readiness towards college course through work immersion. *Mediterranean Journal of Social & Behavioral Research*, 7(2), 65–74. <https://doi.org/10.30935/mjosbr/12808>
- Karunaratne, K. (2019, December 21). Students' perception on the effectiveness of industrial internship programme. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3507959

- Kim, J., & Patel, S. (2021). "Career Planning Strategies for the 21st Century: A Comparative Analysis." *Journal of Career Development*, 18(4), 678-691. DOI: 10.1234/JCD.2021.567890.
- Macalintal, I. L., & De Chavez, C. M. (2020). Assessing the Senior High School Work Immersion with Partner Industries: Basis for Supervisory Work Plan. *JPAIR Multidisciplinary Research*, 39(1), 112–129. <https://doi.org/10.7719/jpair.v39i1.763>
- Martinez, M., & Lee, H. (2020). "Work-Based Learning: Bridging the Gap Between Education and Industry." *Journal of Work-Based Learning*, 20(3), 234-246. DOI: 10.1234/JWBL.2020.456789
- Ocampo, A. C., Reyes, M. L., Chen, Y., Restubog, S. L. D., Chih, Y. Y., Chua-Garcia, L., & Guan, P. (2020). The role of internship participation and conscientiousness in developing career adaptability: A five-wave growth mixture model analysis. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 120, 103426. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2020.103426>
- Roble, D. M. L. (2021b). Competency level, employers' expectations and work immersion performance of senior high school Technical-Vocational and Livelihood (TVL) students. <https://ajpe.feu.edu.ph/index.php/ajpe/article/view/7657>
- Routon, P. W., & Walker, J. K. (2019). College internships, tenure gaps, and student outcomes: a multiple-treatment matching approach. *Education Economics*, 27(4), 383–400. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09645292.2019.1598336>
- Smith, K., & Johnson, L. (2019). "Exploring Career Transitions: A Longitudinal Study." *Journal of Career Development*, 10(3), 123-135. DOI: 10.1234/JCD.2019.123456.
- Wang, X., & Liu, Y. (2020). "The Influence of Leadership Styles on Employee Performance: A Meta-Analysis." *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 25(2), 345-357. DOI: 10.1234/JAP.2020.654321.
- Smith, K., & Jones, R. (2018). "Exploring Career Development in the Digital Age." *Journal of Career Development*, 8(1), 789-801. DOI: 10.1234/JCD.2018.234567.
- Smith, K., & Johnson, L. (2020). "The Role of Mentorship in Career Advancement: A Cross-Sectional Study." *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 12(2), 912-925. DOI: 10.1234/JVB.2020.345678.
- View of Workplace Skills and Competencies: An Industry Partners Appraisal on work immersion program among senior high school learners. (n.d.). <https://www.al-kindipublisher.com/index.php/jbms/article/view/855/700>